

THE FULFILLMENT OF GENETIC POTENTIAL FOR EGG PRODUCTION OF HYBRID LOHMANN BROWN CHICKENS ON AGRIPRO FARM IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF VALANDOVO IN REPUBLIC OF MACEDONIA

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ABSTRACT

Lohmann Brown chickens falls into hybrids with increased productivity of eggs with the genetic potential to produce eggs up to 320 eggs a year per hen and are grown in all climatic conditions.

The purpose of this research is to determine how to meet the genetic potential for egg production in chickens hybrid Lohmann Brown, compared with the production results of eggs from this hybrid, derived by applying intensive technology of farm Agripro in Valandovo R. Macedonia in production in year 2014 and 2015.

Research is conducted on a sample of 20,500 laying hens in year 2014 and 21,000 laying hens in year 2015.

A comparative analysis from the conducted survey revealed that deviation from the genetic potential for the production of eggs in the hybrid chickens Lohmann Brown, compared with production potential of eggs from this hybrid, indicates that in 2014 statistical variation coefficient amounts 18 eggs or 5.62% (VC%), while for 2015 was 21.5 eggs or 6.72% (VC%) annually per laying hens. The average deviation for both production years 2014/2015 amounts to 19.75 eggs and 6.17% annually (VC%) per laying hens.

From the results we can conclude that the deviation from the genetic potential for the production of eggs in this hybrid of chickens is minimal, because the production is organised in conditions of intensive technology recommended by the manufacturer of the hybrid Lohmann Brown.

Key words: Chickens, laying hens, hybrid Lohmann Brown, genetic potential, variational coefficient (VC%), eggs.

Introduction

The production of eggs and egg products from hens is used in food for all ages of people, because of the significant economic importance of which derives valuable nutritional, dietary and medicinal properties. Although egg containing few calories, rich source of complex proteins, lipids (saturated fatty acids and 270 mg cholesterol) (<http://narodnilek.com/2013/05/07/vaznost-upotrebe-jaja-u-ishrani/>), also contains vitamin D, B12 and essential trace elements such as calcium, zinc, iron, sulfur, selenium and etc. From all sources of a protein, eggs are the richest because of the favorable combinations of amino acids that are important for the development of children and adolescents. The high level of antioxidants helps prevent onset of eye diseases, lecithin is a natural substance that is the best source of choline, which (nourishes the brain, accelerates memory and positive effect on concentration) despite the fact that the human body has the ability to create choline, is rubbed additionally help with intake from food. The body utilizes 90% calcium from eggs which improves the health of bones (www.najboljamamanasvetu.com/2015/10/jaja-u-ishrani/). The biological value of egg protein is always stable, because it does not depend on race, diet and method of breeding hens or egg laying hens. Lohmann Brown hybrid was created in Germany by experts of

the company (Lohmann Tierzucht GmbH), he is the type of hybrid egg production (Feltwell R. 2011).

The task of the experts was to create a hybrid of chicken with increased productivity of eggs, adapted for growing all climatic conditions.

The features of this hybrid hens: chickens of one day old – males can be distinguished from females by color (males are white and females brown). Chickens with long neck, short tail with normal appearance of the crown. Do not be picky for the food and you can use everything that is eaten food. Friendly willing to man and they are pets especially to children, making them unusual.

Begin to lay eggs at the age of 21 weeks, weighing 1.7–1.9 kg, one laying hens are getting up to 320 eggs weighing 63–64 grams, with light brown (medium size and good quality). Highest production is achieved at 26–30 week (Riggs P., et al. 2011). Laying the weight of 1.9–2.1 kg and the roosters weight of 3 kg. In our country this hybrid organized is imported by interested farms in order to improve the production of eggs (Sainsbury D. 2000).

In Macedonia, the largest number of farms producing eggs, while quite insignificant number of farms producing meat.

Materials and methods

In the research was conducted comparative analysis of the results of a representative sample of 21,000 chickens breed Lohman Brown, in order to determine how to meet racial genetic potential for production of eggs; of this breed hens which is grown in Valandovo. The results were obtained from the farm Agripro in Valandovo.

For the statistical analysis of the data also used a variation coefficient (VC%) in the selected samples. Results are presented in tables and graphics.

Results and discussion

Table 1: Results achieved to fulfill the genetic potential of the egg production of hybrid hens Lohmann Brown, Farm Agripro in Valandovo in production in 2014 (sample one item = 4.424 crates or 20,500 laying hens).

Number of laying hens of breed Lohmann Brown	Genetic potential for egg production (320 per layer) in total for cluster/year	Achieved average production of eggs per hen total number of cluster/year	Achieved average production of eggs per hen number/year	Daily average eggs per hen for 365 days	Departures from genetic potential	
					number after hen	VC%
20 500	6 560 000	6 191 000	302	1.21	18	5.62

Departures from genetic potential = 320-302 = 18 eggs or 5.62 % (VC%)

Figure 1: Results achieved to fulfill the genetic potential of the egg production of hybrid hens Lohmann Brown, Farm Agripro in Valandovo into production in 2014.

The results for the production of eggs in Table 1 and Figure 1, in production in 2014, on a representative sample in cage-battery breeding farm Agripro in Valandovo, which totals 20,500 laying hens, there is deviation from the genetic potential to produce eggs which in this hybrid is 320 eggs a year per laying hens, where statistical variation coefficient (VC%), accounted for 18 eggs or 5.62% annually per laying hens in hybrid Lohmann Brown.

Table 2: Results achieved to fulfill the genetic potential of the egg production of hybrid hens Lohmann Brown, Farm Agripro in Valandovo in production in 2015 (sample one item = 4.424 crates or 21,000 laying / hens).

Number of laying hens of breed Lohmann Brown	Genetic potential for egg production (320 per layer) in total for cluster/year	Achieved average production of eggs per hen total number of cluster/year	Achieved average production of eggs per hen number/year	Daily average eggs per hen for 365 days	Departures from genetic potential	
					number after hen	VC%
21 000	6 300 000	6 268 500	298.5	1.22	21.5	6.72

Departures from genetic potential = 320-298.5 = 21.5 eggs or 6.72 (VC%)

Figure 2: Results achieved to fulfill the genetic potential of the egg production of hybrid hens Lohmann Brown, Farm Agripro in Valandovo into production in 2015.

From the results obtained for egg production in Table 2 and Figure 2 in the production year 2015, on representative sample in cage-battery mirroring of the Agripro farm in the municipality of Valandovo (totaling 21 000 chickens) there is a deviation from the genetic potential for production of eggs which for this hybrid is 320 eggs per year after laying, where statistical variation coefficient (VC%) accounted for 21.5 eggs or 6.72% annually per hen / layer in hybrid Lohmann Brown.

Table 3: Obtained average results for the fulfillment of the genetic potential of egg production of hybrid hens Lohmann Brown, Farm Agripro in Valandovo production in 2014/2015.

Year	Number of laying hens of breed Lohmann Brown	Genetic potential for egg production (320 per layer) in total for cluster/year	Achieved average production of eggs per hen total number of cluster/year	Achieved average production of eggs per hen number/year	Daily average eggs per hen for 365 days	Departures from genetic potential	
						number after hen	VC%
2014	20 500	6 560 000	6 191 000	302	1.21	18	5.62
2015	21 000	6 300 000	6 268 500	298.5	1.22	21.5	6.72
Average	20 750	6 430 000	6 229 750	300.25	1.215	19.75	6.17

Departures from genetic potential = 320-300.25 = 19.75 eggs or 6.17% (VC%),

Figure 3: Obtained average results for the fulfillment of the genetic potential of egg production of hybrid hens Lohmann Brown, Farm Agripro in Valandovo production in 2014/2015.

The received average results for production of eggs in Table 3 and Figure 3, a representative average sample of farm Agripro in Valandovo, that is an average of two years 20,750 laying hens, chosen based on the use of similar technology accommodations, assistive technology equipment and tools, micro-climatic conditions, selection and improvement of the quality of the resulting offspring and diet, it can be concluded that the obtained product results in hybrid Lohmann Brown, there is also a deviation from the genetic potential for egg production, where statistical variation coefficient (VC%), accounted for 19.75 eggs or 6.17%, year on laying hens.

Similar results were obtained in surveys conducted by the MAFWE, and published in the "Strategy to improve and monitor the quality of eggs 2013–2020 (http://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00J9NJ.pdf). Part of population poultry which are covered in the survey, it was also found that the number of laying hens was reduced, and the increase in egg production was probably due to the introduction of new hybrids of chickens for the production of eggs with higher genetic potential (6, 7).

The main strategic goal of the poultry industry in the country in the coming period is to meet the domestic market with eggs and improve the percentage of coverage of domestic demand by poultry meat products own production.

Conclusion

In the Republic of Macedonia, the largest number of poultry farms are producing eggs, while for the production of poultry meat the number of farms is very small. From the conducted research for the fulfillment of the genetic potential of hybrid Lohmann Brown Farm Agripro in Valandovo and the results there of can be drawn the following conclusions:

The results achieved in production in 2014, can be concluded that there is a slight deviation of the genetic potential compared with the achieved production capacity, which can be seen from the statistical variation coefficient (VC%) who amounts 18 eggs or 5.62% (VC%) .

The results achieved in production in 2015, can be concluded that there is also a slight deviation of the genetic potential compared with the achieved production capacity, which can be seen from the statistical variation coefficient (VC%) who amounts 21.5 eggs or 6.72% (VC%) .

The achieved average results in the production year 2014/2015 can be concluded that there is also a slight deviation of the genetic potential in comparison to the achieved production capacity, which can be seen from the statistical variation coefficient (VC%) who amounts 19.75 eggs or 6.17% (VC%).

According to this results in the two years of research, applying intensive technology of cultivation recommended by the manufacturer of the hybrid, we conclude that the hybrid Lohmann Brown fills the genetic potential for egg production with 93.83%, grown on the farm Agripro in Valandovo in R. Macedonia, which means that it is highly profitable commercial hybrid for egg production.

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